

Advanced Context-Sensitive Access Management for Edge-Driven IoT Data Sharing as a Service

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The Internet of Things (IoT) is becoming increasingly ubiquitous, acting as an important source of real-time data for various applications. By allowing data exchange between various parties along the IoT devices-Edge-Cloud computing continuum, the larger societal benefits of the IoT can be achieved. Assuring security and fostering confidence for IoT data sharing, however, is one of the biggest obstacles. Sharing real-time data originating from connected devices is crucial to real-world intelligent IoT applications, i.e., based on artificial intelligence/machine learning. Such IoT data sharing involves multiple parties for different purposes and is usually based on data contracts that might depend on the dynamic change of IoT data variety and velocity.

We aim to support multiple parties (aka tenants) with dynamic contracts based on the data value for their specific contextual purposes. This work addresses these challenges by introducing a novel dynamic context-based policy enforcement framework to support IoT data sharing (on-Edge) based on dynamic contracts. Our enforcement framework allows IoT Data Hub owners to define extensible rules and metrics to govern the tenants accessing the shared data on the Edge based on policies defined with static and dynamic contexts. We have created an edge-centered architecture that enables multi-tenant use cases with tenant-specific application deployment and IoT-context-based data sharing on edge servers.

Our proof-of-concept prototype for sharing sensitive data such as surveillance camera videos has illustrated our proposed framework. The experimental results demonstrated that our framework could soundly and timely enforce context-based policies at runtime with moderate overhead. Moreover, the context and policy changes are correctly reflected in the system in nearly real-time. We have addressed the need to enable multi-parties IoT (data) resources to be shared based on contracts, especially with dynamic IoT contexts, for tenant applications on the edge to allow their closer access to data.

CCS Concepts: • **Computer systems organization** → *Cloud computing; Peer-to-peer architectures; Real-time system architecture; Embedded systems; Redundancy; Robotics*; • **Software and its engineering** → *Domain specific languages*; • **Security and privacy** → *Domain-specific security and privacy architectures*; **Access control; Authorization**; • **Networks** → *Network reliability*.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Context-Aware Data Sharing, IoT, Edge Computing, Multi-tenancy, SaaS

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1 INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) is creating a major disruption in society by connecting and perceiving physical entities and the environment digitally [11]. But this is only the end of the beginning because, so far, a significant portion of IoT data is used in silos within the same system. There has been limited cross-domain data sharing. In a very broad perspective, Fortune Business Insights estimated that the global IoT market is expected to grow from USD 662.21 billion in 2023 to a staggering USD 3,352.97 billion by 2030¹. This reflects a significant growth trajectory for the IoT market in the coming years, indicating a robust expansion of IoT technologies and their applications across various sectors. Enabling real-time IoT data sharing to connect organizations, customers, suppliers, or other stakeholders can even bring greater added value to different stakeholders in the IoT ecosystems [19], especially those empowered with artificial intelligence/machine learning (AI/ML) applications, which are increasingly deployed at the edge due to the benefits of performance, real-time responses, and data regulation compliance. Therefore, it is essential to support stakeholders in securely and efficiently sharing the live stream, real-time, or near real-time IoT data based on data context. Such IoT data sharing can unleash great potential when stakeholders in different sectors can use the data for their context-specific business and applications, e.g., in smart cities scenarios [33, 34].

Companies often view their data as a competitive asset. Sharing it across domains might risk losing control over this valuable resource. There is also the question of who benefits from the shared data and how its value is distributed among stakeholders. Until now, the most common IoT data-sharing model typically centers around Cloud-based data storage and processing platforms. However, for many of today's scenarios, data sharing must happen at the Edge [45] to facilitate Edge analytics and avoid complex data security and privacy issues. Furthermore, the Edge-computing level will allow tenant applications, especially cross-sector edge AI services and federated ML with private data, to operate effectively and enable trustful on-demand data acquisition. A well-known challenge in this data sharing at the Edge is *real-time, context-sensitive* data access control for different stakeholders. Each stakeholder has a different contract, which may be based on the context of the data that is dynamically changed at runtime. Moreover, the operations in these services are normally automated in real-time; therefore, the access control must also be adapted dynamically in real-time.

Existing approaches for IoT data marketplaces, such as [25, 46], provide mechanisms to share data; however, they have not addressed the challenges mentioned above for access control based on dynamic contexts. Indeed, context-aware IoT data-sharing platforms have been surveyed in detail in [13]. In [17], the authors propose a context-aware security framework that integrates context management with access control policies like XACML [43] for secure data-sharing decisions among smart object groups based on contextual data. However, it does not address Edge-based enforcement for data sharing in dynamic contexts. Some studies have leveraged the IDSA's reference architecture [18] for data sharing. Gimenez et al. [16] highlight their INTER-IoT solution for secure and robust data exchange among port community stakeholders, making it economical and user-friendly. Similarly, [38] introduces a seaport data space for secure and interoperable data sharing, using IDS Connectors and the FIWARE IoT platform to ensure only refined data is exchanged. In summary, no existing approaches provide Edge-based solutions for controlling data sharing driven by dynamic contexts. To the best of our knowledge, no previous access control framework supports dynamic context IoT data sharing for cross-sector IoT smart services. Furthermore, the previous work has not supported the deployment of tenant applications on edge data hubs, thus limiting the flexibility for (pre)processing and aggregating IoT data near its source.

¹<https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/industry-reports/internet-of-things-iot-market-100307>

In this work, we propose a framework that allows dynamic context-driven Edge-based IoT data sharing-as-a-service (EDSaaS) based on contract agreements changeable at runtime. We design and develop a set of Edge-based dynamic context policies representing real-world data-sharing scenarios with access control changes at runtime. Furthermore, these dynamic policies can be enforced and updated in (near) real-time based on the data contexts. With this policy enforcement framework, we enable Edge-based IoT Edge Hubs, which allow real-time data to be collected from various sources regardless of the protocols and data formats, to share data based on context-specific contracts. Our framework can provide the necessary technical enablers for realizing the vision of multi-tenancy edge-based IoT data sharing-as-a-service. In other words, we propose a systematic approach of authentication and authorization for IoT multi-tenancy on the edge with data sharing possibilities between multiple tenants, together with a solution for access control policies that handle IoT's dynamic contexts in a systematic way. We also present a solution to support the deployment of tenant applications in the edge to enable a more convenient data-sharing usage pattern and increase flexibility for close-to-source IoT-data aggregation and inference of IoT-contexts.

This paper is a substantial extension of our previous work reported in [29]. We have improved our approach by facilitating the deployment of tenant applications at the edge, enhancing the convenience of data sharing practices, and providing greater flexibility for (pre)processing and aggregating IoT data near its source and deducing IoT-related contexts. More specifically:

- We introduce tenant-specific access control policy specifications and the enforcement mechanism on the Edge level. The policies and their enforcement are based on data contracts between the Hub provider and tenants, initialized and centrally stored on the Cloud [29]; (Section 3)
- We support context-driven IoT data sharing through the access control policies in flexible ways according to application-level IoT contexts, which are dynamically updated by context-sensing services, i.e., using AI/ML on the Edge [29]; (Section 3)
- Our Edge-based framework can enforce tenant-specific access control policies to the data being shared dynamically according to IoT context changes in the Edge and contract changes in the Cloud [29]. (Section 3)
- As a substantial improvement over our previous work, we improve the conceptual blueprint of EDSaaS with a novel support for allowing the deployment of tenant applications on the edge. EDSaaS supporting multi-tenancy can enable a more application context driven data-sharing usage pattern and increase flexibility for close-to-source IoT-data aggregation and inference of IoT contexts. (Section 3)
- To allow tenants access to shared resources in the edge through in-hub deployed tenant-specific applications, our improved approach reported in this paper suggests an appropriate level of tenant application control and security for ensuring tenant isolation and tenant-specific data sharing. (Section 3)
- Last but not least, we conduct more thorough experiments with policies corresponding to the deployment of tenant applications on the edge. (Section 4)

In the remainder of this paper, we provide a motivating example in Section 2. Section 3 presents our approach, which is evaluated in Section 4. We discuss related work in Section 5. Finally, we give our conclusions in Section 6.

2 MOTIVATING EXAMPLE

Let us take the position of the IoT Data Hubs service provider X , who owns Edge-based IoT Data Hubs (Edge Hub servers) deployments distributed in a smart city for safety support. We note

that in practice, Edge servers can be powerful², although, in the Edge, we cannot have elastic resources as much as we want, like in the Cloud. Each Hub deployment is close to IoT devices, the primary data sources for the Hub considered in this work, and other data systems that X does not necessarily own but instead are owned by different data providers. Each data provider P has its own fleet of IoT devices and systems but offers part or all of its data to the Edge Hubs. Here, we assume that X has made agreements with any P that wants to sell their IoT data via the X 's system and "onboard" P 's IoT data streams to X 's Edge Hubs. P trusts X to find the best way to sell data value through monetary means and social incentives (e.g., support emergencies and health safety enforcement). Then, many IoT data consumers want to use P 's IoT data via X 's Hubs for their businesses. Each consumer C subscribes to the data they want using e-contracts in the Cloud-based system of X where all the IoT data streams from different Hubs are listed for the subscription. Such a hub can be an essential part of the ecosystem of sensing-as-a-service [33] and data marketplaces [10]. Currently, how X , P , and potential consumers establish their market relationships have been discussed in the literature in terms of marketplaces [19]. However, the issues of dynamic access control are still open and challenging.

Let us take an example of video camera data and its analytics, seen in various applications, to elaborate on such challenges of dynamic access control. Assume that camera systems from a street have been "onboarded" to make live video data available to the Hub in that street. These camera systems are typically owned by various stakeholders such as shopping malls, parking garages, city administrations, and safety monitoring companies, each for purposes like security, traffic management, or safety monitoring. Consumers can be city administration, construction companies, and safety monitoring companies, and can sign contracts with X and any P to subscribe to their data but not necessarily get video images because of different contract constraints. The city administration can subscribe to the X 's system to receive the number of people gathering in a specific location by an AI service without accessing the video. A safety monitoring company can get detected data about people, who violate the safety regulations, if needed, e.g., the image of these people but not the whole video. In the other scenario, the local police will be alerted if more than a certain number of people gather, e.g., during a festival event, to prepare for emergency responses³. For example, if more than 20 people were gathering simultaneously in one place, the local police might have access to live video images on the Hub. Otherwise, they can only get the number of people gathering. The number of people gathering in these examples or violating safety regulations is the context generated from the data, and the context value is changing dynamically. Assume that the privacy rule of the city only allows the police to watch live camera images on the Hub if the safety prevention policy enforcement saying no more than a limited number of people can gather in one place (for the sake of explanation) can override privacy rights. The police department may also want to automatically access the camera system to recognize wanted criminals using AI. X supports such cases by allowing some tenant (AI) applications to be deployed in X 's Hub to get close access to data. For example, it is quite popular to run different types of ML pipelines for feature extraction, object detection, or object classification with a video stream on the edge [27]. Note that the camera video images are not transferred outside of the Hub.

The camera system mentioned earlier is just one specific example of IoT data that can be shared. In practice, many other IoT data resources from different sectors can also be shared. This means that direct sharing one-to-one is not suitable for realizing the vision of cross-sector smart services and ubiquitous analytics anywhere [14] where different data sources may even be combined for

²e.g., see <https://www.ibm.com/docs/en/cloud-private/3.2.0?topic=servers-preparing-install-edge-computing>

³Examples of safety and emergency situations: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Seoul_Halloween_crowd_crush and <https://www.nytimes.com/2023/09/13/world/asia/fire-vietnam-hanoi-apartment.html>

new service models. There are also security and privacy challenges that must be addressed. Data and data processing must stay as close to the data source as possible for privacy and performance. For example, in the camera system discussed above, each geographical area needs a local Edge server to receive all data from the cameras in that specific area and control how camera data can be shared for different stakeholders from the Edge.

Note that intelligent Edge Hubs can infer the context of data and can even provide AI data filtering and pre-processing before sending data to the end-users. Thus, multiple data sources can be merged to become new, high-quality data sources.

3 EDGE-BASED DYNAMIC CONTEXT POLICIES

In this section, we first describe our EDSaaS model in Section 3.1. Then, in Section 3.2, we present the EDSaaS architecture. Next, an overview of the security control for the tenant-specific applications is given in Section 3.3. We give the details of our data usage contracts and policies specification in Section 3.4, context sensing in Section 3.5, context synchronization in Section 3.6. Finally, we present how to address isolation and data security in Section 3.7 as well as resource and network management aspects in Section 3.8.

3.1 Edge-based Data Sharing as a Service (EDSaaS) Model

In our primary service model, the Edge Hub provider has made agreements and integration in advance with data providers so that the Edge Hubs have the capabilities to extract and sense specific characteristics of the data from providers (without compromising the business sensitivity of data transferred via the Edge Hub). We note that such a hub-based model exists and is common in practice [8, 9]. Moreover, once onboarded to the Edge Hub, the IoT data providers must have already signed a contract with the Edge Hub containing technical details, such as the range of data and the frequency of being sent. On the other hand, Edge Hub can monitor and detect data violations sent by IoT providers so that malicious attackers cannot harm it. Based on these assumptions, our service model mainly focuses on how the Edge Hub can control data sharing as a service for different data consumers (called tenants) based on dynamic contexts.

Technically, context-based policies are used as contracts between the Edge Hub and tenants. The constraints within contracts and the contract itself can be changed based on *contexts* [21, 24]. Hence, relevant *generic contexts and application-specific contexts* are determined through the observability capabilities of the Edge Hub, based on the predefined metadata and data from monitoring/sampling techniques for each data source. To this end, modern Edge Hubs can first leverage AI/ML and data observability techniques to infer specific data-specific contexts for different applications through monitoring plugins and sampling techniques. Second, intelligent IoT data sources can share metadata about provided data to the Edge Hub. The critical business model allows tenants from cross-sectors to get data (driven by IoT contexts) from various data sources managed by the Edge Hub.

3.2 System Architecture

Fig. 1 depicts the architectural design of our proposed EDSaaS framework. One central policies management system in the Cloud-based server (on the right-hand side of Fig. 1) will be able to manage many Edge Hubs (on the left-hand side), in which tenant applications could be deployed.

The Cloud part of EDSaaS consists of the following components:

- *Authentication service* is responsible for authenticating users and tenant-users.
- *Access control policies database* stores the defined access control policies.

Fig. 1. EDSaaS Edge Hub architecture

- *Messaging System* is used to synchronize IoT context data and policy updates between the Cloud and the Edge. This scalable messaging system serves many synchronization tasks between multiple Edge Hubs and the Cloud.
- *Policy transformation service* subscribes to access control policy changes, transforms high-level policies defined as contracts in the *Access control policies* database to the low-level policy format, and publishes them to the messaging queue for enforcement at the Edge level.
- *Context-based interpretation worker* is a service responsible for receiving context data from Edge and looking up the tenant contracts (from *Access control policies* database) that depend upon the context data to generate *tenant-specific context data*, and then publishing IoT-context data specific to the tenants that have access control policies that rely on them.

On the left-hand side of Fig. 1, we show the main component of each Edge Hub.

- *Tenant-applications* are applications from multiple tenants deployed in the *Edge Hub*. These applications subscribe to the Edge Hub's Data service according to the tenant-specific access control policy. Moreover, they are limited in communicating with external services.
- *Forward proxy* provides a proxy function for requests from the tenant applications to reach external services. The proxy authenticates and authorizes the proxy requests using the Authentication service and the local Edge-based Policy Decision Point (PDP).
- *Data service* gets data from multiple data sources and serves as the Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) to provide data access for the tenant applications.
- *Context sensing*: a service responsible for publishing the IoT-contexts to the messaging queue whenever the contexts are published to the Data service.
- *Local Edge-based Policy Decision Point (PDP)*: the PDP plays mainly the role of serving the PEP on accepting or denying the access requests.
- *Synchronizer*: a service that pulls data (e.g., policies) from the messaging queue and updates the OPA instances with the IoT-context data and the policies.

3.3 Tenant-specific applications on Edge and security control

We leveraged the XACML reference architecture [43] in our access control policy enforcement approach, with some system entities residing in the cloud and some in the edge. Resources are accessed and shared using the Edge Hub's PEP, which depends on the access decision from the PDP, a component that uses the tenant-specific request including contextual data to validate

against the corresponding tenant-specific policies. Residing in the Cloud, we have the database containing access control policies as the Policy Administration Point (PAP), which handles tenant policy creation and modifications. Finally, we have Synchronizer, Worker, Policy Transformation Service, and Messaging System responsible for synchronizing policy information and policy updates between the Edge and Cloud. This design allows the Data Hubs service provider to connect and manage multiple Edge Data Hubs from a central place. It is based on the assumption that the edge and the cloud connectivity is maintained whereas the unavailability of the cloud is minimal and several techniques can be used to deal with connectivity/service problems between edge and cloud [7]. Our architecture separates access control policy retrieval and administration to reduce communication between Edge and Cloud services when enforcing policy rules.

Policy enforcement. On data access and publish requests, the Edge Hub authenticates the tenant using basic authentication credentials from the request and then queries the PDP for authorization, where the specific action on the resource is authorized based on the synchronized access control policy rules and the dynamic data available in the OPA instance.

As mentioned, our approach follows the usage control model since the use cases often involve continuous access patterns. We can prevent indefinite access after prior access rights by re-authorizing by setting a time configuration in the streaming service and re-authorizing before forwarding packets. Hence, we rely on the best practices and adjust configurations for short-live authorization expiration as it is a well-known problem that specific configurations must be tested for specific deployments [20, 37]. Every successful authorization result is cached for performance purposes. To prevent misbehaving tenants from exhausting the network resources and reduce the overall risk of system overload, we have an *obligation*, a built-in context *data_amount*, which is generated internally based on the tenant's data consumption and provisioning.

Policy administration. To make policy definition systematic and simple, we use a Domain-specific Language (DSL) in combination with template engines to render specific terms in a Rego template (see Section 3.4). Whenever an access control policy is created or updated, the policy generation service renders the DSL-defined access control policy in suitable templates to generate policies and then publishes them to the Messaging System. Our Edge Hub subscribes to the Messaging System to replay and consume access control policy change events. The policies are then fed into the PDP to be used for authorization requests.

3.4 Data Contracts and Policies Specification

This section presents the data contract models, the corresponding policy specifications, and the synchronization between them.

3.4.1 Contracts. There are many models for data contracts of IoT services in the literature. In our work, we leverage and extend the common Identify and Access Management (IAM) concept [39] to define the contract model with the following aspects.

- *Principal/Id* represents the identification of the tenant.
- *Name* describes the overview of the contract.
- *Effect* specifies the permission of a given resource such as Allow and Deny.
- *Resource* indicates the list of the IoT resource IDs that the contract affects.
- *Actions* specifies the tenant requests such as publish and subscribe.
- *Conditions* specifies constraints based on some attributes that are dependent on runtime inputs such as system-wide or application-level contexts. We support two types of conditions: *AnyOf* and *All*, which can be combined to include multiple specific conditions based on the attributes.

We use JSON to define the contract model. Listing 1 illustrates a simplified example of a tenant-specific contract, i.e., Tenant 1's. In this example, city surveillance video data is only visible to Tenant 1 (for safety monitoring) if more than 30 people show up simultaneously. For another tenant, e.g., a fire department—Tenant 2, the contract for viewing city surveillance video data is defined for rescue missions only when fire alarm A is triggered (Listing 2).

```

1{  "tenant": "tenant-1",
2    "contracts": [
3      { "Name": "Allow streaming camera based on people count threshold OR
4        violence detected",
5        "Action": [ "subscribe" ],
6        "Effect": "Allow",
7        "Resource": [ "/smartcity/camera/stream/country_x/city_y/store_z/
8          city_surveillance" ],
9        "Conditions": {
10         "AnyOf": [
11           { "object": "people_count", "location": "store_z",
12             "max_5mins": { "gt": 30 } },
13           { "object": "violence_detection", "location": "store_z",
14             "violence_last_1mins": { "gt": 0 } }
15         ],
16         "All": [
17           { "object": "data_amount", "protocol": "mqtt",
18             "lasthour_mb": { "lt": 3000 } },
19           ...
20         ]
21       }
22     ]
23 }

```

Listing 1. Tenant 1's contract example

3.4.2 Tenant-specific enforcement policy. Once the Edge Hub provider establishes a tenant contract, a specific instance of the contract for the tenant is generated and stored in our Access control policies database. The contracts in JSON format will be transformed into a low-level policy format that can be used for the PDP in the Edge Hub to make decisions per data access request.

```

1{  "tenant": "tenant-2",
2    "contracts": [
3      { "Name": "Allow streaming camera when fire alarm triggered",
4        "Action": [ "subscribe" ],
5        "Effect": "Allow",
6        "Resource": [ "/smartcity/camera/stream/country_x/city_y/store_z/
7          city_surveillance" ],
8        "Conditions": {
9         "AnyOf": [ { "object": "fire_alarmA", "location": "store_z",
10                    "alarm_last_5mins": { "gt": 0 } }
11         ],
12         "All": [
13           { "object": "data_amount", "protocol": "mqtt",
14             "lasthour_mb": { "lt": 2000 } },
15           ...
16         ]
17       }
18     ]
19 }

```

Listing 2. Tenant 2's contract example

```

1 package app.iot
2
3 default allow = false
4 default whitelist = false
5 allow{ whitelist }
6
7 whitelist {
8     #Validate-Action
9     some i
10    actions := ["subscribe"]
11    actions[i] == input.action
12    #Validate Resource
13    some j
14    resources := ["/smartcity/camera/stream/country_x/city_y/store_z/
15                  city_surveillance"]
16    regex.match(resources[j], input.topic)
17    #Validate Condition AnyOf
18    var_any_c_0 := data["context_data"]["people_count"]["store_z"]["max_5mins"]
19                > 30
20    var_any_c_1 := data["context_data"]["violence_detection"]["store_z"]["
21                  violence_last_1mins"] > 0
22    conditions_anyof := [ var_any_c_0, var_any_c_1 ]
23    some k
24    conditions_anyof[k] == true
25    #Validate Condition AllOf
26    var_all_c_0 := data["context_data"]["data_amount"]["mqtt"]["lasthour_mb"] <
27                3000
28    conditions_allof := [ var_all_c_0 ]
29    conditions_allof_negative := {value | value = conditions_allof[_]; value ==
30                false}
31    count(conditions_allof_negative) == 0
32 }

```

Listing 3. A tenant-specific policy example in Rego language transformed from the contract in Listing 1

There are two main approaches to the logic code for checking the permission and making the decision at a PDP. The first approach is to have an all-in-one code to evaluate the permission based on the contracts of all tenants. However, this approach might require a complex implementation that can cover all contract cases. The second approach is to generate logic code for each tenant from the contract information, making the code have smaller footprints. We chose the second approach because of the benefits of lightweight decision points, such as the ease of changing the logic code and the speed when evaluating the permission.

To demonstrate the second approach, we use Open Policy Agent (OPA) [4] for policy enforcement with runtime parameters and leverage its Rego policy language to define the policy. In OPA, the Rego policy is employed to evaluate the runtime context. While the runtime data changes frequently, the Rego policy is created during the initialized process and only re-created/updated when the contract is updated. Listing 3 shows the Rego policy example used in our framework. This Rego policy is transformed from and corresponds with the contract described in Listing 1.

The Rego policy must be updated to the PDP in the Edge Hub when a tenant contract is established or changed. Therefore, we need an automated process to synchronize a tenant contract to the PDP. To this end, we have developed a method to transform the contract defined on the cloud management side (in JSON presented previously) to the logic code in the decision points (Rego

file) on the Edge Hubs. The generation process is triggered independently per tenant at the first deployment time or when the tenant's contract changes at any point in time. We describe this transformation process below.

3.4.3 Generation and synchronization of tenant-specific enforcement policy. The process involves four components in both the Cloud and the Edge Hub. First, the *Policy Generator* component contains the primary logic to transform the low-level policy into the Rego policy. Next, the *Messaging System* transmits the generated policy from the Cloud to the Edge Hub, and the *Edge Synchronizer* component listens to the corresponding messages from the Messaging System to update the Rego policy to the OPA component (the PDP).

The *Policy Generator* component is the most critical and challenging in this flow. Typically, a tenant has multiple contracts that define their permissions to various IoT data sources in different context-based conditions. We implement a set of rules as a template engine that supports converting the meta-model and the context structure into a Rego policy. The template engine in the *Policy Generator* component is extensible with new conditions and context information. Therefore, our system can handle a new type of contract without changing the entire framework. The *Policy Generator* transforms each tenant contract separately into a final Rego file (*tenant-specific policy*) using the white-listing and black-listing approach. This approach requires an operation, i.e., a resource access request must meet the action, the resource, and the conditions specified in the policy before checking the decision between allowing, denying, and neutral. Beyond that, the final decision is made after going through all policies. Resource access from a tenant is only authorized if at least one allowed policy matches while no one is detected.

Because many Edge Hubs are connected to the Cloud part, we need a scalable mechanism to synchronize data contexts and enforcement policies between the Cloud part and the Edge Hub. To this end, we use the Apache Kafka framework [1] to implement the *Messaging System*. The *Policy Generator* component will send the generated tenant-specific policy to a topic of the Messaging System with the payload of the Rego policy and the tenant's identification. We note that some components of the Kafka framework might not be suitable for certain edge configurations; however, we assume that the Edge Hub with context sensing is a part of the network where a Kafka consumer/producer will be executed.

3.5 Context Sensing

The *Context Sensing* component evaluates the context related to data and generates context data based on the observability of metadata and real-time data of IoT data sources. Context sensing is carried out in the Edge, whereas the context data, which is usually updated only when the situation changes, is light. Our framework supports two primary IoT contexts: system and application-level contexts.

3.5.1 System-wide contexts. This context category is about typical, well-understood attributes of data usage such as data amount, times, and duration. These contexts are real-time but independent of the data values. For example, the daily volume limit to access camera data is a system-wide context. We define these system-wide contexts in the high-level policy specification for tenant contracts. Listing 4 provides an example of a system-wide context policy with a volume-based context that limits hourly data access to 3,000MB and daily access to 30,000MB. The context sensing component will update the context data based on relevant system events to synchronize with the OPA enforcement component.

3.5.2 Application-level contexts. There are different types of real-time data from a data source that can generate contexts for the policies. These include raw data from sensors such as temperature or

```

1 "All":
2 [{"object": "data_amount", "protocol": "mqtt", "lasthour_mb": {"lt": 3000}},
3 {"object": "data_amount", "protocol": "mqtt", "last24hour_mb": {"lt": 3000}}]

```

Listing 4. Volume-based policy configuration

data generated by AI services from IoT devices such as the number of people or an accident captured in a camera. We also leverage these application-specific contexts for our policy specification, similar to system-wide ones. For example, Listing 5 illustrates such an application-specific context policy that involves a threshold policy with the number of people.

```

1 "AnyOf":
2 [{"object": "people_count", "location": "store_z", "max_5mins": {"gt": 35}},
3 {"object": "fire_alarm", "location": "store_z", "alarms_last_5mins": {"gt": 0}}],

```

Listing 5. An example of application-specific context: people count

There are two main approaches to implementing context sensing. The first approach allows both raw and context data to go through a proxy or gatekeeper as a context sensing before forwarding it to end-users. The second approach is to fan out two data flows, one used for context-sensing, the other main data flow going to be forwarded to the end-users if the OPA-based PDP approves it. In this work, we employ the second approach by developing a *plugin* API for each type of context data. By doing so, we can add new *plugins* to generate new context data when there is a new context type from a new data source.

A common principle of a context-sensing *plugin* in the *Context Sensing* component is to listen to the fan-out data flow in the *Data Gateway* to capture the selective IoT data used as context data. To generate runtime context data as a context-based variable described above, the *plugin* can use an aggregation method (e.g., average, sum, max, min) for system-wide contexts or employ an AI component (e.g., for people count) for application-level contexts. The *Context Sensing* component will send these runtime generated values to the *Messaging System* on the Cloud. Upon receiving a context data message, the *Messaging System* will trigger the *Context-based Integration Worker* component to generate the tenant-specific context data based on tenant contracts of relevance. The tenant-specific context data are synchronized back to the Edge to enforce the corresponding context-based policies.

3.6 Tenant-specific Context Data Generation and Synchronization

Fig. 2 depicts the entire data flow and process of using context data from a data source to generate and update the corresponding tenant-specific context data for runtime policy enforcement.

In the first step, the *Context Sensing* component listens to the *Data Service* to capture the selective IoT data to be used as context data. Then, we develop aggregation methods (i.e., average, sum, max, min) for some given windows (i.e., 5 minutes, 15 minutes, last hour, and last 24 hours) to create context-based variables as described in Section 3.5. Finally, we transmit these variables to a communication channel via a Kafka topic to deliver the context data from the Edge Hubs to the Cloud. Table 1 shows the samples of the existing window-specific variables that are selected to be used as the tenant-specific context variables later on. Note that this list is extendable with new contexts. Although we currently implement the method manually, it can be replaced or integrated with other existing lightweight solutions, e.g., Quix Streams⁴.

⁴<https://github.com/quixio/quix-streams>

Fig. 2. Sequence diagram of tenant-specific context data generation

Table 1. Edge Hub contexts variables

Attribute	Primary Index	Context variables	Description
data_amount	rtmp mqtt	lasthour_mb , last24hour_mb lasthour_mb , last24hour_mb	The data throughput accumulated
people_count	store_z	max_5mins , min_5mins, avg_5mins ,max_15mins min_15mins, avg_15mins	The aggregated people count
fire_alarm	store_z	alarm_last_5mins alarm_last_10mins alarm_last_15mins	Alarms in the last X minutes
violence_detection	store_z	violence_last_1min violence_last_5mins violence_last_15mins	Violences in the last X minutes

The vital component in this process is the *Context-based Interpretation Worker* that listens to context data from the *Messaging System* component to generate tenant-specific context data based on tenant contracts. In addition, the *Context-based Interpretation Worker* listens to the corresponding Kafka topic to create a global context database. Based on each tenant contract of relevance, only selected context variables are used to generate an updated version of the tenant-specific context data, as described in pseudo-code in Algorithm 1.

Finally, each generated tenant-specific context data, together with tenant identification, will be wrapped in a payload to be sent back to the Edge Hub via the *Edge Synchronizer* component in the Edge Hub. Similar to the policy synchronization process presented previously, this synchronizer also captures related Kafka topics for tenant-specific context data and updates them to the *PDP* for tenant-specific policy enforcement. Our *PDP* implementation using *OPA* needs both Rego policy (static) and inputs from this context data (runtime) for each tenant to decide the access permission, e.g., allow or deny a given access request.

3.7 Isolation and data security

As we support in-hub deployment for tenant applications to access shared data in the Edge Hub, we need a high level of application control and security from an Edge Hub provider's point of view. As for security, each tenant application must only be able to access its own data space.

Data: Context data, Contracts

Result: Tenant-specific context data are selected for all tenants

forall *tenant's contracts in Contracts* **do**

 read current contract;

 initialize *tenant_context*;

forall *policy rows in current contract* **do**

 read current contract policy row;

forall *context variables in the policy row* **do**

 read current context variable;

if *context variable does not exist in tenant_context* **then**

 extract context variable value from Context data;

 append the read current context variable and its value to *tenant_context*;

end

end

end

end

Algorithm 1: Illustration of the Context-based Interpretation Worker component

Resource management. As mentioned in the previous subsections, we propose using a containerized environment. Not only does it enable interoperability, but it also provides a simple way to manage application resource usage. A containerized tenant application will have to adhere to its run-time configuration, thus being unable to utilize more than the host provisioned amount. Tenant isolation with security and privacy is one of the most important criteria in multi-tenant SaaS [31]. We have to make sure that no tenant app unintentionally or purposely accesses or damages the data of other tenant applications. In this paper, we started to support the simplest form of tenant applications, i.e., the tenant applications are developed and deployed by the Edge Hub owner to do (pre)processing more specifically for a tenant's need. Deploying tenant applications on separate containers for different tenants is very important for tenant isolation. Although tenant separation can be carried out in a variety of ways, in the cloud computing environment, tenant isolation should be handled at the application level with the responsibility of the tenant management based on tenant-specific access tokens [31]. At the edge computing level in the context of data sharing in this paper, we adopt a lightweight approach for tenant isolation at the network level (see below), which leaves a more holistic tenant management approach for future work. We provide more discussion on this point in Section 4.3.

Network management. Restriction of networking capabilities is a more complicated matter, as a container's networking configuration is typically restricted to on/off, or restricted to configuration of internal networking on the host machine. Using existing components in the Edge Hub, e.g., the Data Service in combination with the Forward proxy (Fig. 1) as the *PEP*, we should be able to enforce complex network access policies in the same way we enforce data-access access control policies. By combining container configuration, a forward proxy, and the Edge Hub *PEP*, a given tenant application can be granted access only under certain circumstances, as depicted in Figure 3.

- The container configuration should be configured so that the container is only able to communicate through the forward proxy.
- The forward proxy should authorize every proxy request with the Edge Hub's *PEP*.
- The *PEP* should only authorize requests under given circumstances defined in the policies.

This solution enables a new category of use cases where a tenant application can get partial access to data. As network capabilities are restricted, so is data sharing. However, tenant applications are still able to access and process data in a way that decouples data processing access and sharing rules.

Fig. 3. Forward proxy integrated with the PEP to enforce network policies based on IoT-context

3.8 Resource and Network Management

Resource management. We use Docker Compose⁵ (`docker-compose`) as a containerized environment for tenant-application deployment and management, as mentioned previously. With Docker Compose we can configure service deployments with specific resource constraints. Resource limits constrain the container’s maximum capacity, the maximum amount of resources provisioned by the host machine. Resource reservations set the container’s minimum resource usage, the resources that will always be available to the container; in contrast, the declared limits are not necessarily available as other containers and services may share the host’s resources. To ensure resource isolation between tenants and containers, setting an appropriate resource limit based on the edge server’s specifications and the number of expected applications is important. For example, the service `person_count` can be configured with `docker-compose` resource constraints so that it is restricted to 1/2 CPU core and 50M of memory. The service’s container will always have 1/4 of a CPU core and 20M of memory available to it.

Network management. As described in Section 3, we restrict a container’s networking capabilities and utilize a forward proxy through which the containers can proxy requests. As shown in Figure 3 we use `nginx`, a proxy server [2], configured as a forward proxy, and make use of some specific modules to authenticate and authorize requests using our authentication service and in-hub OPA instances similarly to how we enforce data access requests to the Edge Hub. To restrict the network access of the tenant-application containers, we have configured `docker` networks so that the containers can only communicate with a restricted amount of services. For example, a `docker-compose` configuration can specify that a tenant-application can only access *some* internal Edge Hub services (mainly to get access to data in the Edge Hub), and also the forward proxy, using the networks `edgehub_tenant_apps` and `proxy_network`.

Listing 6 illustrates the `docker-compose` configuration of the `nginx` forward proxy. It has access to all the Edge Hub’s internal services with the network `edgehub_private`, network access to communicate with the cloud services with the network `cloud`, and also declares the strictly internal network `proxy_network`. The volumes declared mount the `nginx` configuration file and the `njs` script for authentication and authorization. `njs` [3] is a scripting language subset of JavaScript,

⁵<https://docs.docker.com/compose/>

which can be used with the `nginx` module `ngx_http_js_module` to handle complex security checks and to modify requests and responses. In our case, `njs` executes sub-requests toward our server for authentication and toward OPA instances for authorization.

```

1 version: "3.5"
2 services:
3   forward_proxy:
4     image: nginx
5     container_name: forward_proxy
6     volumes:
7       - ./nginx_opa_forward_proxy.conf:/etc/nginx/nginx.conf:ro
8       - ./auth_request.js:/etc/nginx/njs/auth_request.js:ro
9     expose:
10      - "80"
11      - "443"
12     networks:
13       - edgehub_private
14       - cloud
15       - proxy_network
16 networks:
17   edgehub_private:
18     external: true
19   cloud:
20     external: true
21   proxy_network:
22     external: false
23     internal: true
24     name: proxy_network
25     driver: bridge

```

Listing 6. Docker-compose forward proxy setup

Listing 6 shows an excerpt of how the Edge Hub is configured to support the tenant-application infrastructure. In this configuration, both the internal Edge Hub service network `edgehub_private` and the strictly internal network `edgehub_tenant_apps` are declared.

Forward proxy internals and usage. The `nginx` proxy configuration declares a location directive that matches every path so that every HTTP request gets proxied to their target URLs and requires that all requests include an internal sub-request to a location that invokes the `njs` script described in Algorithm 2, which performs the necessary authentication and authorization. Two other locations, one for upstream requests for our authentication server, and the other for upstream requests to OPA instances for authorization, are declared for sub-requests from the `njs` script.

The authentication scheme used for proxy requests is *Basic Authentication*. By extracting the `Proxy-Authorization` header⁶, we can authenticate using our authentication server. Using our DSL, the policies are declared with HTTP methods as actions, and target URLs as resources. This way, we can authorize with OPA, by extracting the target URLs and the HTTP methods from the requests.

4 EVALUATION

In the previous section, we have partly shown the implementation choices for our framework. For the *Data Service* at the Edge Hub, we support and implement the MQTT, RTMP, and HTTP Live Streaming protocols. We use MongoDB to store our contracts. We use `Node.js` to implement the *Tenant-specific Policy Generation* and *Context-based Interpretation Worker* components. In addition,

⁶Example of how to use proxies can be found at <https://requests.readthedocs.io/en/latest/user/advanced/#proxies>

```

function AUTH(request)
  credentials ← getBasicAuthCredentials(request)
  action ← getHttpMethod(request)
  targetResource ← getTargetUrl(request)

  if not authenticated(credentials) then
    return 401
  end if
  if not authorized(credentials, action, targetResource) then
    return 403
  end if
  return 200
end function

function AUTHENTICATED(credentials)
  response ← POST/_authenticate
  return response.authenticated
end function

function AUTHORIZED(credentials, action, resource)
  response ← POST/_opa
  return response.authorized
end function

```

Algorithm 2: Forward proxy njs algorithm

we employ PugJS (<https://pugjs.org>) as a template engine that uses static predefined template files to generate the final Rego files. The template files contain static strings and variables, including many functions, using their defined markup language. The prototype is available on GitHub⁷.

4.1 Experiments with tenant contracts and policies

Fig. 4. Evaluation scenario of a camera system in a store department

4.1.1 Experiment settings. We evaluate the effectiveness of our proposed enforcement framework by validating the following significant factors: i) the correctness of tenant contracts transformed into enforcement policy; ii) the synchronization of tenant-specific context data captured and updated in the enforcement system at runtime; iii) the soundness of the enforcement of dynamic policies with runtime contexts for each tenant.

⁷<https://github.com/isseclab-udayton/EDSaaS-prototype>

For this experiment, we use a real-world IoT sharing scenario mentioned in the motivating example in Section 2. In particular, we consider a store with a surveillance camera, as illustrated in Fig. 4. In this system, the store camera video can only be viewed by the surveillance team within that store. The store will be a *data provider* in our system with the data source of the video publishing to the Edge Hub using the RTMP protocol. This scenario has three tenants: an AI company, a local police department, and a local health department. These tenants connect to the Edge Hub to subscribe to the data from the store data provider. Each tenant establishes a different contract with specific runtime contexts. For example, the AI company (*tenant-A*) can only use video data to perform AI analysis during office hours. The health department (*tenant-B*) can only view the camera stream from the Edge Hub if the number of people in the video is, e.g., more than or equals 30 at a time. Finally, the police department (*tenant-C*) can only view the camera stream from the Edge Hub if the number of people in the video is, e.g., more than or equal to 15 in the last 5 minutes. In this example, *tenant-A* has a dynamic contract with a system-wide context, i.e., office hours; *tenant-B* has a dynamic contract with an application-level context, i.e., the number of people; and the contract of *tenant-C* consists of both application-level context (people count) and system-wide context (last 5 minutes).

We have set up the Cloud and the Edge Hub infrastructure on Amazon AWS with *m5.xlarge* instances using Docker. All cloud-related services, such as the Kafka and database (MongoDB) clusters, are deployed in an EC2 instance to simulate the Cloud infrastructure. On the other hand, we leverage four *m5.large* instances to set up the MQTT clusters and Edge Hub-related services. In our experiments, we simulate the scenario described in Section 2 by developing corresponding applications representing the data providers and tenants in the system. Besides the key components developed and described in Section 3, we have developed context sensing plugins, including an AI-based plugin extracting people count (application-level context) from video and an aggregation service generating system contexts such as average, sum, max, and min. We deployed the applications and service components to an *m5.xlarge* instance on Amazon using Docker Compose. In the Cloud, we use a Docker Compose cluster to deploy the *Messaging System*, and another Docker Compose cluster for the *Context-based Interpretation Worker* and *Tenant-specific Policy Generation* components.

We performed the experiments on two Raspberry Pis with an attached camera to validate runtime performance and functionalities. We use a recorded video showing many variations of people as a data source in our system instead of live camera data.

4.1.2 Dynamic policy enforcement with runtime context data. We have tested our system in two levels of data amount: 1) a recorded video as a data source and 2) a simulation of 20,000 sensors that produce one message per second. We observed that runtime context data from our context sensing component is generated correctly and synchronized in real-time with the PDP through our cloud-based services to enforce the dynamic policies properly.

In particular, in our experiments, the health department can watch the video through the Edge Hub only when the number of people detected in the video is 30 or greater. The video permission is denied/revoked if the threshold is not reached. Similarly, according to the contract, the police department (*tenant-C*) can only access the video if the number of people in the video in the last 5 minutes is equal to or greater than 15. Our experiment showed that the runtime context data of people count within the last 5 minutes are adequately generated and updated. As a result, this tenant has access permission when the context variables reach the threshold.

4.1.3 Performance and Overhead. We set up two MQTT clusters, each of which has four nodes using *m5.large* instances, to evaluate the performance and overhead of our framework. The first cluster has only the authentication mechanism. The second one integrates with our policy enforcement

Table 2. Context Change Propagation time (in ms)

	Earliest Receiving Time	Last Receiving Time	Extra propagation time for a new tenant
Maximum	103	275	2.3
Minimum	36	155	1.05
Average	46	210	1.64

mechanism and the OPA module for authorization per event of publishing a message, subscribing to a topic, and forwarding a message to a subscriber. We also set up an instance for benchmarking two clusters using an MQTT stress testing tool. To compare the overhead in two clusters, we used the tool to publish to both clusters with the frequency of 20,000 messages per second by simulating 20,000 MQTT clients publishing one message per second in a minute. On the other hand, 20,000 MQTT clients subscribe to fetch all messages. Noticeably, the publishing rate is static, and both clusters can handle that rate. We measured the overhead by evaluating the receiving rate. The median receiving rate times without and with our policy enforcement are 82,969 messages per second and 70,801 messages per second, respectively, resulting in 17.2% in the overhead of the enforcement mechanism. We noticed some outliers in the result produced by the cluster with OPA integrated. In our observation, the overhead is acceptable for authorizing the tenants on every request.

We also performed experiments to evaluate the response times of our system when a policy or a context value is changed at runtime. We measured the time from the policy update to the database to when it is propagated to the OPA module. We performed the test 10 times to get the average numbers. For rendering the Rego policies update in the database, it responded almost immediately without delay. However, the average time to deliver the policies over the network to update to the OPA took around 18.5 ms.

In the third experiment, we evaluate how the system scales with a larger number of tenants when a context is changed. We tested with 100 tenants on propagating the context value from the data source to the OPA policy module. In this context-change scenario, we set a timer starting when the context changes until it is evaluated and published to the OPA. Since a context change may affect many tenants, we measured the propagated time of the first and the last tenants among 100 of them. Table 2 describes the times we measured. On average, for over 100 tenants, it took about 1.64 ms to process and update the new context to an OPA instance.

4.2 Experiments with policies for the deployment of tenant applications

4.2.1 Experiment settings. In our evaluation scenario 2, a fire department can deploy a tenant application that consumes directly data from the Edge Hub (Fig. 5). Sensor data from smoke detectors, heat cameras, video cameras, and other devices can together help form a decision about whether the context of a fire taking place is actual and also provide additional information to the fire department before dispatching firefighters. In the case of an actual fire, IoT-context data can be transmitted to the fire department for them to assess risks, get an overview of the severity, and more. An IoT-context that the fire department would like to be more informed about is the amount of people currently present at the time and location of a fire, however, due to privacy reasons, sensitive data can only be shared when there is a fire.

The fire alert scenario includes the facility owner as a data producer and the fire department as a data consumer and tenant application owner.

Fig. 5. Fire detection scenario implementation

The authorization flow includes the following steps::

- (1) The data flows from the surveillance camera to the data service, which is consumed by the tenant application *fire context service* and the Edge Hub’s *fire detection service*.
- (2) When a fire is detected by the *fire detection service*, it publishes an IoT context *fire_detected*, which is synchronized to the cloud and back to the Edge Hub before ending up in OPA as context data.
- (3) Finally, the *fire context service*, which has been processing the people count from the video feed and is subscribed to the *fire_detected* context, is allowed to pass on the people count to the fire department’s systems over HTTP.

To validate that our approach and proof-of-concept can be used for the fire alert scenario, we define some requirements that should be met:

- (1) The Edge Hub should enable sharing between the facility owner and the fire department without adding additional infrastructure from the fire department to the location.
- (2) The Edge Hub should respect the defined access control policies and enforce them according to the defined rules.
- (3) The facility owner’s privacy should be preserved.
- (4) The Edge Hub should enable the fire department to gain additional information regarding the current situation in cases of fire, in addition to being alarmed about possible fire.

IoT contexts. We have two main IoT contexts that are relevant for this scenario. First is the IoT context of a fire at the location, the *fire_detected* context. This IoT-context is provided by the Edge Hub provider, as an opt-in feature and will be published whenever an in-hub service registers enough signals from the data published to the Edge Hub. Then we have the *people_count* context, an IoT-context provided by the fire department’s tenant application. In this scenario, the *people_count* context will not be used further in the context of the Edge Hub, but can be made available to other

tenants and tenant-applications. Instead of consuming the IoT-context from the Edge Hub, the fire department relays the IoT-context directly from the tenant-application using HTTP. Because we will use the *fire_detected* context in our access control policy (defined later in this section), we first have to declare this IoT-context in our system. Listing 7 declares the IoT-context with specific locations coupled to a topic that it will be published to.

```

1 {
2   "fire_detected": {
3     "location_x": {
4       "topic": "/smartcity/fire_detected/location_x"
5     }
6   }
7 }

```

Listing 7. Fire context

Tenant applications. For the scenario, we let the fire department use two different kinds of applications. An in-hub tenant-application *fire_context_service* deployed in the Edge Hub, and a Cloud-application *fire_context_server* representing the system that the fire department uses to collect insights regarding current fires. The *fire_context_service* is responsible for the transmission of data to the *fire_context_server*, in this case, the person counts, which it transmits using an HTTP endpoint exposed by the *fire_context_server*.

In addition, we have an in-hub application that publishes the *fire_detected* context, the *fire detection service* owned by the Edge Hub provider. From a conceptual point of view, it is a separate type of application as the Edge Hub provider owns it, however, in our proof-of-concept, it acts as a tenant-application owned by the tenant representing the Edge Hub provider.

4.2.2 Pre-enforcement setup. Before data sharing can be initiated, we first have to make the right arrangements. First, the cloud application *fire_context_server* must be running, tenant applications that are relevant for this scenario must be deployed to the edge, then the access policies that allow sharing must be defined.

Access policy definition. The relevant access policies for this scenario are:

- The access policy allows the tenant application *fire_context_service* access to the video feed.
- The access policy allows the tenant application *fire_context_service* access to the *fire_detected* context.
- The access policy that conditionally allows the *fire_context_service* to reach the HTTP resource exposed by the *fire_context_server* whenever *fire_detected* has been published.

We define the access control policies with our DSL as shown in Listing 8, which will later be transformed with pug-templating into rego policies that OPA can evaluate. The transformed rego policy is depicted in Listing 9.

Tenant application deployment. As mentioned in previous sections, our proof-of-concept uses docker-compose heavily. This also includes the Edge-PaaS. From the Edge Hub provider's perspective, the tenant application's source code is delivered by the fire department, reviewed, and finally built into an artifact as a docker image. A docker-compose.yml file for each tenant is then shipped to the Edge Hub; this YAML file includes the reference to the docker image artifact stored in the Edge Hub provider's docker image repository, as well as all the necessary memory and network configurations.

```

1 {
2   "tenant_name": "fire-department",
3   "policies": [
4     {
5       "Name": "Subscribe to the video feed",
6       "Effect": "Allow",
7       "Action": ["subscribe"],
8       "Resource": ["/smartcity/camera/stream/location_x"]
9     },
10    {
11      "Name": "Subscribe to the fire_detected context",
12      "Effect": "Allow",
13      "Action": ["subscribe"],
14      "Resource": ["/smartcity/fire_detected/location_x"]
15    },
16    {
17      "Name": "PUT request to http://fire-department.com/people_count",
18      "Effect": "Allow",
19      "Action": ["PUT"],
20      "Resource": ["http://fire-department.com/people_count"],
21      "Condition": {
22        "AnyOf": [
23          {
24            "object": "fire_detected",
25            "location": "location_x",
26            "last_5mins": {"eq": 1}
27          }
28        ]
29      }
30    }
31  ]
32 }

```

Listing 8. A fire department's policy definitions declaration

4.2.3 Enforcement. After the access control policies have been updated in the cloud PAP, the JSON-based access control policies get transformed into rego policies and then distributed to the Edge Hubs, ending up in the OPA instances. Already at this point, the two non-conditional policies grants the *fire_context_service* access to the video feed and the *fire_detected* context. When the video feed is published, the *fire_context_service* begins the inference of the *people_count*. At any point, the *fire_context_service* could try to relay the *people_count* to the *fire_context_server*, however the request would be denied at the forward proxy as the *fire_detected* context is not yet published. To reduce the amount of failing requests the *fire_context_service* subscribes to the *fire_detected* context and refrains from sending requests until the context has been published. Finally, when the *fire_detection_service* publishes the *fire_detected* context, the *fire_context_service* begins sending HTTP PUT requests to *http://fire-department.com/people_count* (see Listing 10). When the request reaches the forward proxy, the proxy begins to authenticate using basic authentication credentials from the header and then begins the authorization process after successful authentication, by extracting the HTTP method as *action* and the target URL as *resource*, using the OPA instances. If the authorization process is successful, the *fire_context_server* will receive *people_count* message.

Looking back at the requirements we defined earlier, we can see that the approach fulfills most, if not all, of the requirements to a certain extent.

```

1 default allow = false
2 default whitelist = false
3
4 allow{
5   whitelist
6 }
7
8 whitelist {
9   some i
10    actions := ["subscribe"]
11    actions[i] == input.action
12
13    some j
14    resources := ["/smartcity/camera/stream/location_x"]
15    regex.match(resources[j], input.topic)
16 }
17
18 whitelist {
19   some i
20    actions := ["subscribe"]
21    actions[i] == input.action
22
23    some j
24    resources := ["/smartcity/fire_detected/location_x"]
25    regex.match(resources[j], input.topic)
26 }
27
28 whitelist {
29   some i
30    actions := ["PUT"]
31    actions[i] == input.action
32
33    some j
34    resources := ["http://fire-department.com/people_count"]
35    regex.match(resources[j], input.topic)
36
37    var_any_c_0 :=
38      data["context_data"]["fire_detected"]["location_x"]["last_5mins"]
39      == 1
40    conditions_anyof := [ var_any_c_0 ]
41    some k
42    conditions_anyof[k] == true
43 }

```

Listing 9. Transformed policies

- (1) The case study shows that data sharing between the facility owner and the fire department is possible by defining the correct access control policies and that the fire department is able to collect the data without additional infrastructure setup, by utilizing the tenant-application's networking capabilities.
- (2) We have verified that the Edge Hub enforcement works according to the defined access control policies by showing that the fire department is unable to share data until the `fire_detected` context has been published.

```

import requests
def send_people_count():
    proxies = {
        'http': 'http://forward_proxy:80',
        'https': 'http://forward_proxy:443'
    }
    headers = {
        'Proxy-Authorization': 'fire-department:123456',
        'Proxy-Authenticate': 'Basic',
        'Content-Type': 'application/json'
    }
    response = requests.put(
        'http://fire-department.com/people_count',
        json={'msg': f'location_x people count: {people_count}'},
        proxies=proxies,
        headers=headers
    )
...

```

Listing 10. *fire_detection_service* HTTP request

- (3) The facility owner's privacy is preserved to an extent. At least to the point where we can argue that the benefits gained trump the comforts of privacy. With enough data, the *fire_detection_service* would have fewer false positives, and the *fire_context_service* would only get access when necessary.
- (4) The normal behavior of fire detectors, like smoke detectors, is that the fire department is alerted after a fire alarm has rung for a longer period. As shown with the proof-of-concept, the collection of additional information, such as the amount of people in a room, is possible.

4.2.4 Performance benchmarks. We carried out performance tests, including (i) the data access policy enforcement performance, (ii) the dynamic context update performance, and (iii) the tenant application network restriction performance. As mentioned in the earlier sections, we have used docker-compose to deploy our proof-of-concept. Although we could distribute and run the Edge Hub, tenant-application, and forward proxy specific *YAML* configurations on an edge server like a *Raspberry Pi*, and the cloud-specific infrastructure and management application configuration in the cloud using a cloud provider like *AWS* (Amazon Web Services), we have chosen to simplify the setup by running it all on a single machine. The hardware specifications of the machine used for the experiment are Intel Core i9 (2,3 GHz 8-core), AMD Radeon Pro 5500M (8GB), Intel UHD Graphics 630 (1536 MB), 32 GB DDR4 (2667 MHz), 1TB SSD (2.3GHz). Our measurement methods involve sampling seven independent measurements, sorting them, and finally highlighting the median measured value. This is done to accommodate for variance resulting from cold starts, CPU context switching, garbage collection, etc.

Edge Hub data enforcement overhead: To measure the performance of the data access enforcement we have created two applications, one that publishes data, and one which subscribes to the data. The times measured are calculated by calculating the difference between publish from the first application, to reception in the latter application. The first column in Table 3 shows the measured time while the enforcement was disabled, measured in milliseconds, while the second column shows the measurements where the access control policy enforcement was enabled. Figure 6 depicts plotted values from Table 3. This benchmark was done to show the overhead created by the enforcement system. As we can observe, the enforcement has an initial cold-start delay, however, the delay is

Table 3. Enforcement overhead: Median of average message end-to-end delay measured over 7 runs, with various number of concurrently sent messages

	Without enforcement (ms)	With enforcement (ms)
10 messages	0.040	1.200
100 messages	0.160	0.580
1 000 messages	0.153	0.329
10 000 messages	0.039	0.204
100 000 messages	0.025	0.195

reduced by caching and made less significant with more messages. Considering the overall low latency to transmit a message, we find that the overhead is acceptable for the enforcement of data access.

Fig. 6. Enforcement overhead

Real-time dynamic context update. Measurement of the context update performance was done using an application with context update publishing capabilities, and modifications of the Edge Hub synchronizer. The times measured are the differences between the timestamp of context update publishing and the timestamp after the OPA document update.

End-to-end delay (ms) measured over 7 runs with a single context update each run is [510, 676, 1110, 1407, 3625, 4546, 4848]. Using the median, we estimate that the end-to-end delay is approximately **1,4 seconds** with minimal network transmission delay. The measured update latency is relatively high, even without network transmission time. In the upcoming section, we will discuss the lack of performance.

Forward proxy overhead. To measure the tenant-application network policy enforcement we created a tenant application running in the Edge Hub and an application running on the host machine which the tenant application is to communicate with over HTTP. As the tenant application is running on Docker, and simulating a different deployment environment than the host application,

we had to use the host's local IP address assigned by the router as our loopback address. This had to be done as localhost seen from the tenant-application's perspective loops back to the container instead of the host. To show the overhead of our forward proxy solution, we ran three independent setups. The first setup had the tenant application go directly to the host application without using the forward proxy. The second used the forward proxy as a pass-through, meaning it did not authenticate nor did it authorize the request. The third setup used the forward proxy with full policy enforcement capabilities enabled. The times measured were the difference between the timestamp at which the HTTP request was made and the timestamp of when the host application received the message. All measurements are shown in Table 4. The first column shows the delay without any proxying, the second column shows the pass-through proxy measurements, and the third column shows the delay with enforcement enabled in the forward proxy. The results show that the forward proxy enforcement adds a relatively high amount of latency.

Table 4. Forward proxy overhead: End-to-end delay measured over 7 runs with a single message each run

Without forward proxy (ms)	Pass-through forward proxy (ms)	Forward proxy with enforcement (ms)
4	5	83
4	5	92
4	5	92
4	6	94
4	6	95
6	8	118
37	71	125

4.3 Discussions on Policies Co-Evolution & more possibilities for Edge-based Services

4.3.1 Policies evolution: Our proposed framework can support the (co-)evolution of Edge-based services and policy enforcement. When a new IoT data provider partners with the Edge Hub, their data schema and protocols will be “synchronized” with the Edge Hub system. In other words, the onboarding process for new IoT data providers is done in the background. The IoT data provider can work closely with the Edge Hub provider to ensure their data are adequately available to the Edge Hub. Our focus is on the process of new tenants subscribing to new data sources and accessing new data according to tenant-specific dynamic contexts. For example, let us consider an updated scenario when *Tenant 1* is updating its contract (Listing 1) so that its system can access surveillance cameras' data in case of fire. For this existing tenant, the additional context is the status of the fire alarm triggered. This means that there will be an updated policy in the contract database that extends the existing policy with the newly added context based on the fire alarm status (Line 4, Listing 11).

```

1 "AnyOf":
2 [{"object": "people_count", "location": "store_z", "max_5mins": {"gt": 30}},
3 {"object": "violence_detection", "location": "store_z", "violence_last_1mins": {"gt":
4 0}}
5 {"object": "fire_alarmA", "location": "store_z", "alarms_last_5mins": {"gt": 0}}],

```

Listing 11. An example of an updated policy

The rest of the enforcement is propagated from the new contract in the Cloud for generating the updated Rego policy, which is then synchronized into the OPA engine in the Edge.

4.3.2 Advanced contexts and trustable data sharing: Nowadays, there are many advanced and dynamic contexts available in practice that can be deployed and integrated into our proposed framework. For example, we can have many dynamic contexts in emergencies, such as fire alarms, floods, and traffic accidents. These contexts can also be imported from or provided by machine learning applications (in today's deployment, such applications can be executed within IoT devices, e.g., smart cameras and drones).

Our framework can especially lay a foundation for end-to-end dynamic industrial data sharing with traceability, trust, and security. In advanced scenarios where supply chain stakeholders call for an innovative way of trustable data sharing across companies, the dynamic contexts of data sharing (used in OPA for authorization) and other key (business critical) transaction data can be stored in a traceability layer. Distributed ledger/blockchain and smart contract technologies will ensure traceability and integrity of the data (including data quality), enabling trustworthy and secure data exchanges. Our framework can be extensible with such a traceability layer by implementing a secure proxy/connector integrated with the data service to allow all stakeholders to contribute to the same ledger/blockchain of the supply chain/ecosystem.

Our framework uses OPA for policy decisions, which is very popular in the industry, including OPA for the Cloud and network. Therefore, our proposed framework is compatible and can be integrated into existing industrial ecosystems. However, in order to facilitate its integration into standardised data space ecosystems, our EDSaaS architecture may be combined with the most recent IDS Reference Architecture model (IDS RAM). EDSaaS could provide a lot of added values on top of IDS RAM because the most recent IDS RAM does not completely support Edge-based architectures and flexible, context-driven access control models, which are essential for controlling a range of applications in data space ecosystems.

4.3.3 More advanced multi-tenancy scenarios for EDSaaS: In this paper, we initiated an approach for supporting the simplest form of tenant applications, i.e., the tenant applications are developed and deployed by the Edge Hub owner to do (pre)processing more specifically for a tenant's need. In principle, there could be a catalog of pre-built applications provided by the Edge Hub owner for the end-users of EDSaaS to choose and use for (pre)processing data according to their need right on the edge before sharing the processed data output to them. In more advanced scenarios, it would be even possible for third-party tenant applications, which must be checked in sandbox environments before on-boarding for the deployment on the edge. In a related work, there is a holistic tenant management approach for this direction in the cloud computing environment [31]. However, we have not addressed these advanced scenarios in this context of edge computing in this work reported here.

5 RELATED WORK

IoT Data Marketplace or Sharing is very common in IoT infrastructures where data are collected from multiple providers and can be shared with customers or other stakeholders [6, 15]. Several frameworks and architectures for IoT Data Marketplace or Sharing have been proposed in the literature. For instance, in [15], the authors introduced a framework enabling multiple data suppliers to engage with data consumers, including AI applications and IoT service providers. The proposed framework emphasized the advantages of standardization, promoting replicable solutions across various IoT segments. It also highlighted the significance of interoperability and introduced novel business models within multistakeholder ecosystems. Abbas et al. [6] surveyed the state-of-the-art data marketplace research, consisting of 133 academic articles discussing data marketplaces and their research proposals and prototypes with computational pricing and architecture. A few primary studies have leveraged the IDSA's reference architecture [18] for data sharing. Gimenez et al. [16]

highlight their INTER-IoT solution, which facilitates secure and robust data exchange among port community stakeholders, positioning it as an economical and user-friendly option for both stakeholders and system integrators. Similarly, the authors of [38] introduce a seaport data space that enables secure and interoperable data sharing between stakeholders. Their approach employs IDS Connectors and the FIWARE IoT platform to process data (e.g., cleaning, filtering, aggregation) at the edge before sharing, ensuring that only refined data is exchanged rather than raw data.

IoT Data Marketplace or Sharing is typically based on data contracts among multiple stakeholders in the ecosystem; thus, as we consider in this work, data access control policy and enforcement are essential to guard the data access for security, privacy, and business contracts. Ouaddah et al. [32] introduced the SmartOrBAC model for access control in IoT using XACML (eXtensible Access Control Markup Language). The system employed RESTful APIs for policy enforcement, ensuring seamless integration with IoT devices; however, no context in the policy is considered. Similarly, in [17], the authors present a context-aware security (conceptual) framework with context management that makes use of context information and access control policies (e.g., XACML [43]) for secure data sharing decisions. They propose a secure data-sharing mechanism for groups of smart objects according to contextual data. However, their framework does not address Edge-based enforcement solutions for controlling cross-sector data sharing driven by dynamic contexts. In the same direction, the authors of [12] propose an Edge-centered context sharing architecture. This study described an architecture that makes security decisions based on shared context information from multiple domains. However, this architecture is only a conceptual model without any concrete enforcement solutions. Nazir et al. [28] employed ontology for context-aware security in the IoT marketplace using OWL (Web Ontology Language) to define security policies for logical decisions among IoT nodes in a healthcare system. Using a context-awareness methodology, the authors addressed different parameters in the framework, including authentication, access control, authorization, and privacy.

Context awareness is another crucial concept for intelligent IoT applications, which must understand the context from sensing data and perform computation accordingly in autonomous ways, i.e., using artificial intelligence/machine learning (AI/ML) [13, 23, 40]. In [40], Sezer et al. delved into context-aware computing and its evolution in IoT and discussed machine learning algorithms for context recognition. De Matos et al. [13] discussed context-aware systems that translate data into contextual information and provide context-sharing solutions to distribute context information. The work examined the requirements for the sharing of context information and context-sharing platforms. In [23], Matos proposed an edge-centric context-sharing architecture based on an edge-to-fog approach, emphasizing low-latency data processing. Edge nodes utilized lightweight data compression algorithms to reduce bandwidth usage. Context sharing involves the MQTT protocol, which ensures real-time data propagation, and provides context-aware security services with the shared context information. Pradeep and Krishnamoorthy in [35] presented a new framework with context modeling that involves data structures like trees and graphs. Middleware implementation utilizes message queues for real-time context propagation, ensuring efficient system performance. Muñoz proposed an architecture for context-aware data analytics in smart spaces [26] with big data processing using Apache Hadoop and Spark frameworks. Additionally, secure data sharing was facilitated through encrypted communication protocols. In [17], the authors propose a context-aware security framework that combines context management with access control policies, such as XACML [43], to facilitate secure data-sharing decisions. Their approach introduces a mechanism for secure data sharing among groups of smart objects based on contextual data. However, it does not address Edge-based enforcement solutions for managing cross-sector data sharing driven by dynamic contexts. Our work on context-specific policy access controls can contribute to sensing-as-a-service scenarios such as utilizing (cross-sector) multi-parties IoT (data) resources to

accommodate large numbers of consumers. Nguyen et al. [30] uses the gatekeeper design pattern that deploys a policy enforcement instance for each tenant application in the Edge. The gatekeeper works as a gateway by intercepting all incoming requests, decoupling access control logic from the application's business logic, and enabling real-time policy updates by redeploying the gatekeeper. However, no dynamic IoT context is supported in their approach. D. Preuveneers et al. [36] make use of the UMA OAuth 2.0 extension that extends OAuth 2.0 from only authorized applications to access on a subject's behalf (person-to-self), to allowing person-to-party (person-to-person and person-to-organization) authorization by delegating access to third parties such as other individuals or organizations [5]. To define and enforce access policies in [36], the policy execution engine Open Policy Agent (OPA) [4] is used. OPA uses a JSON-based policy language named *Rego* that is efficient in terms of parsing and policy size [36]. Even though the approach in [36] follows the same direction as our work and also uses OPA for the policy enforcement engine, it does not yet show the support for utilizing (cross-sector) multi-parties IoT (data) resources to accommodate large numbers of consumers.

There are quite some IoT Data Marketplace approaches such as [22, 41, 42, 46] that focus on using blockchain technology and/or smart contracts to enable data sharing. Perez and Zeadally [34] discussed issues and proposals to use smart contracts in crowdsensing. Sober et al. [42] proposed a blockchain-based data marketplace, leveraging smart contracts to facilitate decentralized data trading. This approach mitigates trust issues and privacy concerns associated with centralized solutions, establishing a foundation for secure and efficient data exchange in IoT ecosystems. Overall, these works, e.g., [22, 46], adopted blockchain/smart contracts for IoT data sharing for no trusted parties. However, these approaches do not touch upon IoT data sharing for trusted parties in which shared data is based on contracts via an intermediary and with dynamic contexts that can bring significant value to the involved parties. The approach in [22] also employs an efficient proxy re-encryption mechanism, ensuring that the data is only visible to the data owner and the person in the contract. Similarly, by employing the blockchain as an auditable and distributed access control layer to the data layer, the authors of [41] enable secure data sharing and resilient access control management. Truong et al. [44] proposed a framework for IoT Data sharing with access control policies and decisions stored and processed using blockchain technology. Blockchain technology can verify to ensure that policy changes, e.g., in smart contracts and access requests, are correctly enforced and publicly auditable. However, the framework did not discuss the context-aware aspects of the policies as we address in this work. In addition, blockchain technology does not support tenant application deployment or integrate well with real-world IoT providers as we discussed. Unlike these blockchain/smart contract-based approaches, our framework offers real-time adaptability, ensuring timely enforcement of context-based policies with moderate computational overhead.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we have presented a framework for context-driven Edge-based IoT data sharing-as-a-service based on authenticating and authorizing multiple tenants in IoT settings at the Edge computing level. The architecture of our framework facilitates the deployment of tenant applications directly within the Edge Hubs. This arrangement ensures that the Hub oversees the sharing of IoT data with external tenants, while also managing the deployment and execution of tenant applications at the Edge. This setup is crucial to optimizing the utilization of real-time data. This framework is designed to streamline data-sharing processes, enhancing the efficiency of gathering and analyzing IoT data directly at its source and enabling more accurate interpretation of IoT-related contexts. At the edge-computing level, our framework is particularly adept at supporting cross-sector edge AI services and federated machine learning with private data. It ensures the effective operation of tenant applications and fosters trustworthy, on-demand data acquisition. Ultimately,

our framework serves as a key technological enabler, laying the groundwork for realizing the concept of multi-tenancy, edge-based IoT data sharing as a service. Our proof-of-concept prototype demonstrates the practical application of the proposed framework. It successfully implements and enforces dynamic context-based policies for accessing IoT data at the Edge, tailored to the specific needs of different tenants. This prototype not only validates our framework's efficacy but also illustrates its potential for accessing and utilizing IoT data in a multi-tenant environment.

Carrying out further tests is crucial. Many configurations and effects are known but specific to the deployments that we have not performed. Some important aspects are: the resilience and availability of the centralized cloud under critical situations, the sensitive of access control expiration and refreshment under time configurations and network/service failures, and context sensing for diverse types of data under different conditions. Enhancements to our framework could significantly boost its scalability. By refining our implementation, we can further optimize its performance to accommodate larger and more complex IoT environments. On the other hand, our EDSaaS model can be integrated with the latest IDS Reference Architecture Model to ease its adoption as part of standardized data space ecosystems. Flexible, context-driven access control models and Edge-based architectures are crucial for managing a variety of applications in data space ecosystems, but they are not fully supported even by the latest IDS Reference Architecture Model. Additionally, integrating our framework with Data Marketplace models, and leveraging blockchain and smart contract technologies presents a promising avenue. This integration would enable the secure recording of transactional provenance in context-based IoT data sharing. Such a combination would greatly strengthen the framework's trustworthiness for all participating entities. By utilizing these technologies, key transactional data, including application-level contexts, system-level contexts, and data quality metrics, can be securely documented by default. This approach not only ensures data integrity but also fosters a more transparent and reliable environment for IoT data transactions.

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